

EARTH SCIENCES

USE OF RADAR SATELLITE DATA FOR THE MONITORING OF SNOW COVER

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Abstract

The paper considers the theoretical and practical aspects of exploring the snow cover in a MW band as applied to the SLR facility of the first National man-made satellite «SICH-1». The results obtained from the thematic imagery processing and recommendations with respect the snow melt dynamics prediction are presented.

Keywords: radar sensing; radio wave backscatter; snow cover.

1. Introduction

The snow cover has a substantial effect on the man's everyday life, since its presence is primarily responsible for the energy and water balance of the Earth's surface, which is of vital importance in solving the issues of agriculture, hydrology, ecology, etc.

The intensity of the spring - time floods is in many ways dictated by the snow melting rate. The melt water is conducive to overfilling the water reservoirs and swamps, replenishing the ground water storage, weighting the soil, thereby providing the stored soil moisture whose amount is of great significance for the future harvest. Here, it should be noted that in spite of the benefit derived from the increased water storage one is actually faced with the losses of time and material resources, which are caused by the need to have the drainage system cleared of the snow and by the after-effects resulting from the inundation of economic areas.

Typical of the snow cover is the high spatial variability of physical properties, which is brought about by the macro-, meso- and micro-scale processes in the atmosphere, the type of terrain, and vegetation cover, etc. The snow accumulation within a single climatic region proceeds in a certain fashion peculiar to specific landscape conditions, etc. In this case, the vegetation cover which is in fact the governing factor in the spatial variability is in itself acted upon by this particular phenomenon. The influence of various types of forests in the snow accumulation has been thoroughly studied.

The snow cover thickness is one of the basic characteristics, since there is a relationship between the thickness of snow and its properties, specifically, the linkage to the thermal conditions and, consequently, to their ability to shut out the Earth's surface from external effects. Although the temperature gradients and the resultant snow cover metamorphism appear to be pronounced at a small snow layer depth, the uniformly

thick snow cover undergoing different stages of metamorphism may differ in temperature under the like weather conditions.

Snow may exhibit various physical properties depending upon the form of crystals. As the snow cover is becoming compact, its thickness and thermal conductivity tend to vary. Therefore, it is necessary to allow for its properties throughout the whole period of its existence. Here, of prime importance are the early periods of snow cover formation, snow melting and, what is more essential, the periods involving the drastic variations in the snow cover, resulting in the temperature drops.

Among other no less significant features of the spatial snow distribution is the snow coverage area. The in-situ measurement techniques do not often permit them to be adequately determined, especially in the areas having a small number of observation stations.

The development of the remote sensing methods for exploring the snow cover made it possible to take a new approach to the observation procedures and the analytical treatment of the data being obtained.

It should be pointed out that the optical remote sensing methods involving the use of aerospace carriers, i.e. aerial photography, optical and IR scanners, have gained wide acceptance. However, the efficiency of their application is found to be significantly limited by the requirement for the optical transparency of the atmosphere in a region as the measurement session is being well under way.

The radar - seriented techniques for remote sensing of the snow cover in a MW band have provided the basis for the aerospace radars of the «Cosmos-1500» type [1-3] and have proved to be free from thus limitation.

In the 80s and 90s the studies that were performed with these systems made it possible to predict the processes of spring- time snow melting and the floods on rivers as well as other critical events in the practical

work based on the data collected from the first National satellite «SICH-1» [4].

2. The peculiar features of radar sensing of the snow- covered land surface

The electromagnetic wave backscattering recorded by the satellite- based SLR in the winter-time is largely dependent upon the scattering in the snow layer which represents the conglomerate of ice crystals in the atmosphere. In this case a crucial role is played by the radio-wave scattering effects at the «air-snow» and «soil-snow» boundary. Therefore, while analyzing the observations results the effects of volume and surface scattering should be taken into account.

If the snow cover is present the positive radar brightness contrast between the objects such as river valleys and the territories between two rivers, as observed.

This phenomena is due to the fact that, with the snow cover being present the basic contribution the magnitude of the specific radar cross section (RCS) can be made by the following scattering mechanisms: scattering from the rough «air-snow» boundary, scattering from the volume (internal) snow inhomogeneities, scattering on the rough «snow-soil» boundary [5].

Normally, the scattering from the subsurface soil inhomogeneities can be neglected because of the screening effect of the above-mentioned tree scattering mechanisms.

The relative contribution of the above- listed scattering mechanisms may vary depending upon the snow cover thickness and structure, the temperature of snow and soil and their moisture level and other factors (including time of day). One of the basic parameters specifying the nature of radio wave scattering by the snow cover is the radio wave penetration depth (skin-layer thickness) [6]:

$$\delta = \frac{\lambda \sqrt{\varepsilon'}}{2\pi \varepsilon''} (\varepsilon'' \ll \varepsilon') \quad (1)$$

As is obvious from [6] the real part σ^l is not virtually temperature- and frequency- dependent and is actually a function of the snow density only ρ_s varying from $\varepsilon^l \approx 1.2 \text{ g/cm}^2$ to $\varepsilon^l \approx 2.8 \dots$ at $\rho_s \approx 0.8 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Density, in its turn, is governed by the snow-fall conditions (the wind speed, temperature, etc.) and by the variation in the hydrometeorological conditions over the whole period starting with the snow cover formation and ending with its observation.

The attenuation of radio waves as they propagate in the snow is determined by the loss tangent,

$$tg\delta = \varepsilon''/\varepsilon' \quad (2)$$

whose value at a frequency of $\approx 5 \cdot 10^4$ to $\approx 2 \cdot 10^4$ with a temperature ranging between -5° C and -30° C .

Substituting the values ε' and ε'' in formula (1) for ε we find that in the case of dry snow the skin-layer thickness may be as much as several meters. Assuming that the volume snow mass inhomogeneities (elementary scatters) are uniformly distributed in depth, one can arrive at the conclusion that the RCS magnitude associated directly with the volume scattering is in direct proportion to the thickness of the snow cover which is

dry and uniform in depth. Here, the "air-snow" boundary can be ignored for, two reasons: firstly, there is a "slight" contrast at the "air-snow" boundary and, secondly, the snow surface is relatively "smooth" in a cm wave band (in comparison to the roughness of the open soil surface).

As regards the scattering at the "snow-soil" boundary, the contribution of this mechanism at the negative temperatures also appears to be considerably attenuated, because the values ε of the snow and the frozen-through soil are close to each other. These values are basically determined by the electromagnetic ice parameters (when the free moisture is non-existent). As the snow temperature and its moisture M_v increase (with the emergence of free water) the absorption in the snow shows a significant increase (at $p_s \approx 0.25 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $M_v \approx 2\%$ and a frequency of 10 GHz the value ε'' increases by 3 orders of magnitude and as high as ≈ 0.1). In this case δ is reduced to a few centimeters; as a result, the scattering from the soil surface becomes fully screened by a sufficiently thin snow cover. With the negative temperatures followed by the positive ones, and particularly at the period of intensive snow melting, a contrast inversion is certain to occur between the river valleys and the areas between the river, i.e. the vast tracts of weekly snow with a weekly developed (practically smooth) surface appears, especially in some water-filled areas, should result in a sharp decrease of the RCS in comparison to the rougher surface of the "air-snow" boundary (wet soil) in the areas between rivers. Here, the dependence δ_0 upon the snow cover thickness since due to the small value δ the entire scattering process occurs in a thin subsurface layer with a thickness, of at most, 1 cm (for $\lambda = 3\text{cm}$).

3. Scientific and practical work on the use of the radar data from the "sich-1" satellite in performing the hydrological forecasts over a snow-melting period.

A wide spectrum of issues resulting from the study of the Earth's surface includes the due of remotely sensed data for hydrological observations. These issues are associated with the need to monitor the snow cover propagation and melting dynamics, the ice cover status on rivers and inland water basin, to determine the spatial characteristics of the water surface, etc.

It should be pointed out that of really topical interest are the hydrological observations, that are made at the period of the spring-time floods. Snow melting and breaking up of ice on rivers and water basins at this time of year is sufficiently dynamic. Therefore, in order to be able to monitor the existence of floods it is necessary to be provided with operational, current and forecasting information which could be obtained from the space-borne remote sensing systems.

Throughout the winter- and spring- time period of 1996 make scientific studies and practical work aimed at making the "SICH-1" SLR data available to the subdivision of the Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Center (UHC) and other national economy-oriented services at the height of intensive snow melting and spring time flood existence. In addition to the reception and the preliminary radar data processing, a good deal of work

have been done to optimize both the techniques for processing the thematic remotely sensed data from spaceborne radars and the principles of coordination with the UHC subdivision that are engaged in making hydrological forecasts.

The examples of using the radar data for hydrological forecasts are given in Fig.1-2. Fig.1 shows the radar image, acquired by the SLR of the "SICH-1" on March 21, 1996 and the results of thematic processing. According to the observation data provided by the spaceborne radar the position of the snow cover boundary is seen to be in good correlation with the results of snow cover measurements.

Since the ground-based observation stations are relatively sparse, this kind of information is of significant interest while working out the snow melting forecasts.

At the same time the radar image examination indicated that there was a correlation between the radar signal intensity and the thickness and water content of the snow cover.

In further studies this can be utilized to generate thematic maps of spatial distribution of the above-mentioned snow cover characteristics. Fig.1 (the thematic map) presents a separation line of zones featuring the different levels of moisture content in the snow cover. According to the hydrometeorological center of Ukraine (HMCU) the moisture content in the northern region is 40 mm and in the southern over 60 mm, which is shown as a dark color tone. All that is evidenced by theoretical calculations.

Fig.1. Radar image, acquired by the SLR of the "SICH-1" and the thematic map

The radar information acquired by the SLR of the "SICH-1" in the winter-time can also be used to forecast the underflooded areas over a period of spring-time freshets. For instance, the light color tone in Fig.2 (the radar image acquired on February 24, 1996 shows the plain frozen - up flood plains in the basins of the Dnieper and Seversky Donetz rivers). Meanwhile, the floodplains of those rivers are identified as heaving a dark color tone. Here, the spatial dimensions of the frozen - up floodplains and those of the areas in the spring time are practically the same.

The SLR data processing technique that can be employed to estimate the spatial characteristics of the overflow of large water basins using the elements of the

cluster analysis were examined in [3] and utilized in the experiments, involving the use of the SLR of the "Cosmos-1500" series when the adjacent areas of the Amur river were heavily in undated in 1984 [1].

The application of the above-mentioned technique to identify the underflooded zones in the Central part of Ukraine is exemplified in Fig.3 ("a" - the initial image, acquired in spring; "b" - is the image, acquired in the summer; "c" - interpretation of the image "a"). The floodplains of the Vorskla and Seversky Donetz rivers are not virtually identified in the image "b". They are clearly visible in the image that was acquired in summer.

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Fig.2. Radar image

Fig.3 a. Initial image, acquired in spring

Fig.3 b. Image, acquired in the summer

Dniepr

Fig.3 c. Interpretation of the image "a"

Analysis of the radar imagery of the territory of Ukraine, acquired by the SLR of the "SICH-1" over the winter and spring time period of the 1996 suggest that the radar surveying data obtained from space, makes it possible to observe the snow cover propagation dynamics and to define the snow melting boundaries. Besides, the combination of in-situ measurements and the above - mentioned observations may prove to be useful in introducing an operational service to forecast critical events resulting from snow melting processes, overflow of rivers, underflooding of lakes, etc.

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